

Impact of Optimization Algorithms in Detection of Tuberculosis using Transfer Learning

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Abstract— The World Health Organization has identified tuberculosis (TB) as a major public health threat. Delayed diagnosis due to factors like lack of experts and highly accurate diagnostic methods that are relatively expensive contributes to the increasing and the prevailing burden of TB in the developing countries. This may can be addressed with the breakthroughs in Artificial Intelligence (AI) which paved the way for Deep learning to specialize in computer vision fields. The Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), a promising algorithm, has shown potential in medical image recognition applications as effective models for extracting relevant features from images since it does not demand objective-specific manual feature engineering and promotes end-to-end training from extracting features to classification. The limitation of publicly accessible datasets, on the other hand, is a challenge which can be resolved utilizing the Transfer Learning technique. This study uses transfer learning on chest X-rays (CXRs) to detect tuberculosis, from which features are extracted using VGG-19 architecture pretrained on ImageNet and then fed into a classifier for prediction. We prepared and analyzed the performance of the network through accuracy (ACC), area under the ROC curve (AUC) and confusion matrix on Shenzhen dataset. The influence of three different optimizers on the result obtained was assessed and compared.

Keywords— Tuberculosis, Deep learning, Convolutional neural network, Artificial intelligence, Transfer learning, Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep Learning has been supporting the healthcare industry with its ability to process and analyse enormous amount of data without having to compromise on the accuracy or the results. It is neither Artificial Intelligence nor Machine Learning, but the best of both worlds that utilizes a structured and layered algorithmic architecture that can process data in lightning speed. The prominent areas where Deep Learning [1] are used in medical field are medical imaging in the identification of certain rare diseases, chat-bots which can recognize patterns among patient symptoms, algorithms that can identify specific types of tumours and in the detection of specific types of pathology. Also, Deep Learning has an imperative role in providing the healthcare workers with insights that can help in the early detection of diseases.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a deep learning algorithm which accepts an image as input and assign

weights to various aspects of the image and distinguish one image from the other [2]. CNN is widely used in medical image processing especially in the analysis of Chest X-Ray images. The main reason attributed to the increase in usage of CNN [3], [4] and machine learning models is the easiness in the availability of pre-trained networks and datasets which obtain weights and credits from data repositories such as ImageNet [5].

Another crucial factor is the availability of framed networks for parallel processing and GPUs which can be incorporated with cloud services and various standalone facilities. This, when combined with events like ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) [6] has contributed to the development of highly accurate and efficient frameworks for data processing and analysis. Initiated in 2010, ILSVRC has become the basis for many famous Convolutional Neural Networks including the one developed by the Visual Geometry Group (VGG) of Oxford University [7]. Computer Aided Designs (CAD) is in popular demand for the detection of lung related diseases using Chest X-rays.

Immense number of studies are been conducted on Chest X-Ray datasets for the detection and analysis of Tuberculosis and the major demerit of these studies is that they are depending on certain rule-based prediction and classification which can be exclusive for individuals. There is a lack of providing a more global solution, which can bring more accurate results, rather than sticking on to such localized solutions. In addition to this, as the models are working with a limited number of parameters, they might tend to ignore significant parameters which has a huge impact in the results. The application and utilization of CNNs in Digital Image Processing opens a new horizon in the processing of medical images and hence the advancement in the health sector. Convolutional Neural Networks has application not only in lung segmentation, but in brain segmentation [8], pancreatic segmentation [9] and knee cartilage segmentation [10] as well. Moreover, this pre-trained network is found to have high efficiency in the detection of lung nodules also.

The drawbacks in deep learning of publicly available large datasets led to Transfer Learning [11] which is a Machine Learning technique where the knowledge acquired by a pre-trained model is used in another problem domain. The high popularity of Transfer Learning is attributed to the cause that it can make learn deep neural networks with

comparatively smaller amount of data and [12] amplifies the availability of heterogeneous training data. Image repositories like ImageNet has huge number of images that are pre-trained with CNN and we are free to fine tune them based on the requirement to make it more efficient and accurate [13]. This make sure that we do not have to build a model all from the scratch. Another merit being the concept of hidden layers in the structure as these are able to apply many filters and can work on multiple image resolutions which can be used in the identification of hidden patterns in the images [14]. In addition to this, transfer learning as widely used in medical image processing as well for the analysis of Chest X-Ray images and in the early detection of eye diseases and even in the detection of Alzheimer’s disease.

In [15] to evaluate the performance of pre-trained CNN in TB detection from chest X-ray, we compared the performance of four different CNN architectures in three different datasets. The technique opted was transfer learning with fine tuning and found that VGG-19 outperformed in all the datasets in terms of accuracy. The objective of this work is to examine the effects of optimizers when transfer learning technique with fine tuning is used on the result of VGG-19 architecture. The optimizers opted for the comparison are SGD, Adam and RMSprop optimizers.

II. METHODS

A. Dataset

The Shenzhen dataset of the NIH Tuberculosis Chest X-ray dataset was used in our research. In collaboration with China’s Shenzhen No. 3 Hospital, the National Library of Medicine created the Shenzhen dataset[16]. It comprises normal and abnormal X-rays along with tuberculosis manifestations. Shenzhen’s dataset has 662 subjects with and without tuberculosis. The dataset is listed in Table 1. To obtain robust functionality, the model is trained on the dataset.

TABLE 1. DATASET SUMMARY

	Shenzhen
Subjects	662
without TB	326
With TB	336
Male	442
Female	213
Other/Unknown	7

Infiltrates, cavitation, pleural effusion, pneumonia, and a number of other radiological manifestations of tuberculosis can be observed on CXR images [17]. CXRs of patients from the dataset are shown in Figure 1. CXRs of uninfected people are shown in Figure 2 a, while CXRs of individual infected with TB are shown in Figure 2 b.

Fig.1. a) Normal CXR b) Cavitary infiltrates

III. METHODOLOGY

The complete procedure is depicted in Fig. 3 as a conceptual diagram. Loading CXRs, preprocessing and applying augmentation on training and validation images, transfer learning with VGG19 architecture, fine-tuning the model, training new model with different optimizers such as SGD-Adam-RMSprop, generate predictions, and evaluate performance are the steps involved.

Fig.2. Conceptual Diagram

A. Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

Pre-processing is used to remove features that aren’t significant to the identification of tuberculosis and for that data generator manipulations are applied to images during training to create new images. Data augmentation is performed to prevent overfitting by setting the image target size to 128 * 128, batch size to 64, and class mode to categorical.

B. Transfer Learning with CNN

Deep Learning algorithms are extremely effective at classifying images. However, the disadvantage of this architecture is that it necessitates a large amount of data,

computing power, and time. Several deep learning models make the assumption that training as well as the testing data should come from the same distribution. The high cost of gathering and labelling data limits the availability of data in many real-world applications. In such situations, it's critical to remember and reuse previously learned information for a different task, or domain.

Using pretrained networks, the Transfer Learning technique overcomes the challenges that DL algorithms confront. Its goal is to apply the trained parameters from one task to a new, different task. It can not only reduce the time and effort required to obtain training data, but it can also speed up the training process. The weights of CNNs trained on various datasets are publicly accessible for most known architectures. The majority of the available weights were determined by training on ImageNet. The weights of pretrained CNNs can then be fine-tuned or used as a Fixed Feature Extractor. Transfer learning is advantageous because CNN learn more common, low-level features like shapes and edges in early layers and more task-oriented features in later layers.

To leverage transfer learning on a deep convolutional neural network, there are two widely used techniques. The first approach is feature extraction, in which the pretrained model is only used to extract image features for the input of the new classification model, while retaining its initial design along with the learned parameters. To boost extracted image features and to achieve optimal performance on the new dataset, the second strategy allows some changes to the pretrained model like parameter tuning.

The second technique is used in this research. To pretrain various CNN architectures, we use ImageNet, a large-scale dataset containing 1.2 million images in 1,000 different classes. We can't use the pretrained model to extract image features for classification because the images in ImageNet aren't the same as the ones in our dataset. To produce better image features, we must instead fine-tune parameters of the model on our dataset. As a result, the lower-level layers are frozen, and a dense layer is attached to the pre-trained layers that have been retained. As a result, the fine-tuned model generates results for each class and is capable of classifying input images.

The VGG-19 [18] architecture is used, which has already been trained on the ImageNet dataset. Images are scaled to 128*128 pixels with three channels without considering top layers. To fine-tune the model, the weights of the early layers were frozen, allowing only the upper layers to be retrained and the parameters were selected after multiple experiments. The activation function used is Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [19], and to avoid overfitting, dropout [20] is added, with softmax activation function to classify the CXR as normal or infected. With stochastic gradient descent (SGD) [21] as the optimization method, the learning rate of the model was set at .001, and early stopping was developed to cease the training once the model progress was halted. The same procedure is carried out by replacing SGD with Adam [22] and RMSprop [23] optimizers.

So the procedure can be summarized as:

1. Prepare dataset
2. Preprocess data and apply data augmentation in the dataset
3. Load VGG-19 pre-trained model and apply fine tuning
4. Create and train new model with each optimizer
5. Fit the model on the training dataset
6. Generate predictions: normal or tuberculosis
7. Compare the performance of different optimizers in the dataset

IV. RESULTS

The main goal of adopting the transfer learning methodology was to accurately diagnose tuberculosis in CXR images. VGG-19 was used to train the model in the Shenzhen dataset, and it achieved an ACC of 85% and an AUC value of 85% when SGD was employed as the optimizer. It achieved an ACC and AUC of 50% with Adam optimizer and 80% with RMSprop optimizer. True positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) of the model are depicted in the confusion matrix, which aids in further comparison of the best models. Those with the lowest FN get the best results. Table 2 shows the VGG-19 confusion matrix with SGD, Adam and RMSprop optimizers. So, in that perspective, we get the least FN when we use Adam optimizer, but SGD optimizer does an outstanding job in Shenzhen dataset in terms of accuracy.

TABLE 2. CONFUSION MATRIX SUMMARY

CNN	OPTIMIZER	TP	FP	FN	TN
VGG-19	SGD	285	41	55	281
	Adam	0	326	0	336
	RMSprop	308	18	112	224

Training and Validation accuracy and loss graphs of SGD, Adam and RMSprop optimizers are plotted to access model learning performance. Accuracy-loss graph of SGD optimizer is presented in Fig. 3 and Fig.4 respectively.

Fig.3. Training and Validation accuracy with SGD optimizer

Fig.4. Training and Validation loss with SGD optimizer

The receiver operation characteristic (ROC) curve is shown to visualize the model's performance, as it is the most important assessment metric for evaluating the efficiency of any classification model. It is a well-known fact that the greater the AUC, the better the model is at distinguishing between individuals with tuberculosis and those who do not. The ROC curve of the VGG-19 model is presented in Fig. 5, Fig.6 and Fig.7 for SGD, Adam and RMSprop optimizers.

Fig.5. ROC curve of SGD optimizer

Fig.6. ROC curve of Adam optimizer

Fig.7. ROC curve of RMSprop optimizer

Optimization techniques are in charge of lowering losses and delivering the most precise outcomes feasible. Choosing the right optimizer for the problem dealing with is extremely subjective to the use case. In our study SGD optimizer gives better accuracy when compared with the other two optimizers.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a deep learning approach for identifying TB from CXR images using the transfer learning technique. To automatically detect the most distinguishing features from CXRs the VGG-19 pre-trained architecture is used and trained on the ImageNet dataset. For TB screening, the suggested method eliminates the need for manually designed features. Transfer learning overcomes the challenges of working with high-resolution medical images and limited availability of datasets. Our findings back up the idea that deep learning techniques can be utilized to improve disease management by simplifying the diagnostic procedure. We have also investigated the impact of optimization strategies on the accuracy of the model designed to detect tuberculosis disease.

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